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La creatività è un processo complesso che combina intuizione e razionalità, svolgendo un ruolo cruciale nell'innovazione nei campi artistico, tecnologico e scientifico. Il design thinking e le metodologie educative innovative, come il problem-based learning, promuovono il pensiero divergente e le capacità di problem-solving. Tra queste strategie, il progetto capolavoro emerge come uno strumento didattico volto a sviluppare le competenze professionali degli studenti e la consapevolezza di sé. Questo studio, condotto in una scuola secondaria con un campione di 156 studenti, ha esaminato l'impatto del capolavoro sull'orientamento professionale e sulla crescita professionale, con particolare attenzione agli studenti con Bisogni Educativi Speciali. Un questionario strutturato ha rivelato percezioni contrastanti: solo il 15% degli studenti ha riconosciuto un impatto significativo sulle proprie scelte future, mentre il 60% ha considerato più influenti i tirocini e l'orientamento universitario. Inoltre, il 75% ha percepito il capolavoro come un'esperienza accademica piuttosto che un'opportunità concreta orientata alla carriera. I risultati evidenziano la necessità di integrare il capolavoro con esperienze pratiche e collaborazioni con il mercato del lavoro, migliorando i sistemi di feedback per aumentarne l'efficacia. Questo studio suggerisce un approccio interdisciplinare per rafforzare il ruolo del capolavoro, rendendolo una componente più incisiva nei percorsi educativi degli studenti.

ABSTRACT

Creativity is a complex process that combines intuition and rationality, playing a crucial role in innovation across artistic, technological, and scientific fields. Design thinking and innovative educational methodologies, such as problem-based learning, promote divergent thinking and problem-solving skills. Among these strategies, the capolavoro project emerges as a teaching tool aimed at developing students' professional skills and self-awareness. This study, conducted in a secondary school with a sample of 156 students, examined the impact of the capolavoro on career orientation and professional growth, with particular attention to students with Special Educational Needs. A structured questionnaire revealed mixed perceptions: only 15% of students acknowledged a significant impact on their future choices, while 60% considered internships and university guidance more influential. Additionally, 75% perceived the capolavoro as an academic experience rather than a concrete career-oriented opportunity. The findings highlight the need to integrate the capolavoro with practical experiences and collaborations with the labor market, improving feedback systems to enhance its effectiveness. This study suggests an interdisciplinary approach to strengthening the capolavoro's role, making it a more impactful component of students' educational pathways.

Parole chiave: progetto capolavoro, orientamento degli studenti, esperienza pratica, impatto educativo, scelte di carriera.

Keywords: masterpiece project, student orientation, practical experience, educational impact, career choices.

Introduction

Creativity is one of the most fascinating and complex capacities of the human mind; it represents a dynamic process that involves both intuition and rationality (Runco & Jaeger, 2012, p. 92). It manifests in multiple forms, from art to technological innovation, from problem-solving to the design of complex systems, and

is at the core of cultural, economic, and scientific transformations (Csikszentmihalyi, 1996, p. 47). Design thinking represents a structured approach that allows creativity to be channeled into effective solutions, combining intuition and analysis in an iterative, user-centered process (Brown, 2009, p. 38). It is based on a methodology that includes empathy, problem defini-

tion, idea generation, prototyping, and experimentation—processes that stimulate both cognitive flexibility and the ability to tackle complex problems (Dorst, 2011, p. 523).

In recent decades, scientific interest in creativity and design thinking has grown exponentially, with significant contributions from neuroscience, cognitive psychology, and the learning sciences. Recent studies show that creativity can be cultivated and enhanced through specific learning strategies (Sawyer, 2012, p. 65). Neuroscientific research has highlighted the crucial role of connections between different brain areas in generating original ideas, particularly the interaction between the default mode network and the central executive network (Jung et al., 2013, p. 52).

In this context, education and training play a crucial role in providing tools and methods to stimulate creativity and apply it to various disciplinary fields. Innovative pedagogical approaches, such as problem-based learning and experiential learning, have been shown to foster the development of divergent thinking and the ability to solve complex problems (Kolb, 1984, p. 23; Amabile, 1996, p. 78). Integrating creativity into teaching not only improves the quality of learning but also prepares students to face challenges in increasingly complex professional and social contexts (Robinson, 2011, p. 102).

A particularly relevant aspect in education is the use of the concept of the "masterpiece" as a tool for career guidance in high schools. The idea of creating an outstanding work allows students to explore their aptitudes and professional inclinations, providing a concrete experience of design and realization (Wagner, 2012, p. 87). This approach has been integrated into numerous educational programs with positive results, fostering greater awareness of individual skills and possible future choices (Gardner, 1999, p. 56). Moreover, the masterpiece serves as an effective method for stimulating students' sense of self-efficacy and responsibility, offering them a challenge that combines creativity and strategic thinking (Sennett, 2008, p. 135).

The aim of this article is to explore the connection between creativity, design thinking, and learning, analyzing methodologies that encourage the production of personalized works—the so-called "masterpieces." Through a literature review and case study analysis, strategies for developing creative and design thinking will be illustrated, with practical implications for education, research, and innovation. The ability to generate original and innovative solutions is essential for addressing global challenges, and understanding the processes underlying creativity becomes a key element in facing the future with strategic vision and transformative capacity (Florida, 2002, p. 114).

Theoretical Foundations

The concept of creativity has a long tradition of study, rooted in philosophy, psychology, and cognitive neuroscience. Aristotle (4th century BCE) conceived creativity as the result of the active intellect's ability to combine pre-existing ideas into new configurations (Gaut & Livingston, 2003, p. 21). Modern psychology of creativity has identified several theoretical models to explain the creative process, including Wallas' four-

stage model (1926, p. 76) – preparation, incubation, illumination, and verification – and Sternberg and Lubart's Creative Investment Theory (1995, p. 32), which compares creativity to a cognitive investment that values initially undervalued ideas.

In the field of neuroscience, recent studies have shown that creativity depends on the interaction between the executive cognitive system, which regulates attention and control, and the default mode network, which facilitates the processing of original ideas (Beatty et al., 2016, p. 612). Cognitive flexibility and divergent thinking are closely connected to the activity of brain areas such as the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and the superior temporal gyrus (Dietrich, 2004, p. 1015).

Design thinking, as a methodology applied to creativity, is based on the idea that problem-solving is not a linear process but rather iterative and adaptive (Brown, 2009, p. 39). Simon (1969, p. 112) defined design as an activity that focuses on shaping environments conducive to achieving specific goals, while Buchanan (1992, p. 12) highlighted the role of design thinking in managing complexity and fostering social innovation.

The masterpiece-based approach, used in numerous career guidance programs in high schools, allows students to experience the design process firsthand and develop greater awareness of their own skills (Wagner, 2012, p. 88). The combination of creativity, critical reflection, and design thinking not only enables the production of outstanding works but also promotes meaningful and lasting learning (Dewey, 1938, p. 45).

The concept of the "masterpiece" fits perfectly into theoretical models of creativity, becoming the concrete element through which the creative process manifests itself. In the context of Wallas' four-stage model (1926), the creation of a masterpiece clearly follows the identified stages:

- **Preparation:** The individual acquires knowledge, develops technical skills, and gathers inspiration necessary for creating the masterpiece. This stage is crucial for building a solid foundation upon which new ideas can develop.
- **Incubation:** During this phase, the creative process continues at an unconscious level. The artist or designer allows information and ideas to settle, enabling the mind to form unexpected connections.
- **Illumination:** At a sudden moment, a key idea or an innovative solution emerges, guiding the realization of the masterpiece. This stage corresponds to the creative intuition that often characterizes works of excellence.
- **Verification:** Finally, the masterpiece is refined and critically evaluated by both the creator and the target audience to ensure its effectiveness and its aesthetic or functional value.

Similarly, Sternberg and Lubart's Creative Investment Theory (1995) applies to the process of creating a masterpiece through the concept of cognitive investment. According to this theory, creative individuals identify initially undervalued or unconventional ideas, invest time and resources in their development, and, once the value of these ideas is recognized, reap the benefits. The creation of a masterpiece aligns with this

dynamic, as it often involves a work that challenges existing conventions and requires significant commitment to be developed and perfected.

Moreover, the masterpiece-based approach fosters cognitive flexibility and divergent thinking, key aspects in the neuroscience of creativity. The involvement of the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex and the superior temporal gyrus (Dietrich, 2004) demonstrates how the creation of a masterpiece results from a complex interaction between executive control and the spontaneous generation of innovative ideas.

Finally, the masterpiece finds a connection with design thinking, which considers it not only as a final product but as the outcome of an iterative and adaptive process (Brown, 2009). Through experimentation, critical reflection, and the application of design methodologies, the masterpiece becomes a meaningful learning experience, promoting the development of transversal skills and a greater awareness of the creative process.

Research Context

The study was conducted in a secondary education institute located in the Campania region, which includes both technical and vocational sectors. The selection of this institute was made to ensure a representative analysis of the diversity of educational pathways within the upper secondary school system, in accordance with the classification established by Legislative Decree 226/2005.

Within the institute, fifth-year classes from each educational track were selected. In total, the study involved 156 students, without any exclusions, ensuring the highest possible level of inclusivity.

To guarantee the representativeness of the sample concerning key variables, factors such as gender, academic performance, and students' socio-economic background were considered. A preliminary analysis of the composition of the selected classes confirmed an equitable distribution of students according to these factors, reflecting the overall diversity of the school's student population.

The selected classes represented different fields of study. The technical track includes educational pathways such as the technological sector, the graphics and

communication sector, and the tourism sector. These pathways provide training focused on acquiring technical-scientific and practical skills, with an emphasis on innovation and technology, in line with the framework outlined in Presidential Decree 88/2010. Students in this track are prepared both for entry into the job market and for continuing their studies at the university level, thanks to an approach that integrates theoretical and applied knowledge (Indire, 2020).

The vocational track, on the other hand, is characterized by a more practical and operational teaching approach, aimed at direct entry into the workforce. This track includes the industry and craftsmanship for the "Made in Italy" sector, food and hospitality, and services for health and social care. The recent reform of vocational education (Legislative Decree 61/2017) has reinforced this focus, introducing more flexible and customizable pathways in close collaboration with the local production system (MIUR, 2019).

A key aspect of the analysis is the presence of students with Special Educational Needs (SEN). These students require specific support measures due to learning difficulties, disabilities, socio-economic disadvantages, or needs related to linguistic and cultural differences. Their inclusion in the study provided a more comprehensive view of the diversity of students in the institute and the strategies adopted to support their educational journey.

The distribution of students across different sectors and tracks is presented in the table below, which includes the number of classes, gender distribution, the number of SEN students, and the total number of students involved in the study.

The analysis of the two types of educational tracks within the institute allowed for an exploration of the differences in students' school experiences, levels of preparation, and future expectations. This provided a more complete and detailed perspective, contributing to the reflection on the most effective teaching and guidance strategies to meet the needs of a diverse student population (OECD, 2021).

Figure 1

Institute	Sector/Track	Number of Classes	Number of Students (M)	Number of Students (F)	SEN Students	Total Students
Technical Institute	Technological	1	12	10	3	25
	Graphics and Communication	1	11	13	2	26
	Tourism	1	14	10	4	28
Vocational Institute	Industry and Craftsmanship for Made in Italy	1	13	9	5	27
	Food and Hospitality	1	12	11	3	26
	Health and Social Care Services	1	10	12	2	24
TOTAL		6	72	65	19	156

Questionnaire Administration

At the beginning of the school year, a structured questionnaire was administered to the students of the selected classes, with the active involvement of the Tutor teachers. The tutors played a fundamental role in presenting the instrument to the students, providing explanations on how to complete it, and ensuring a favorable environment for participation. Their presence proved essential in minimizing biases in questionnaire completion and improving the quality of the collected data (De Leeuw, Hox & Dillman, 2012).

The administration took place in a controlled setting during school hours to ensure that all students could participate without external interference, in line with methodological recommendations for data collection in educational research (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The questionnaire was completed anonymously, a crucial aspect in encouraging sincere and authentic responses, reducing social desirability bias in the answers (Tourangeau & Yan, 2007).

Bias and Mitigation Strategies

One of the main biases potentially present in data collection is **social desirability bias**, which refers to students' tendency to provide responses they consider more acceptable or desirable rather than those that truly reflect their thoughts or behaviors. To reduce this effect, the questionnaire was structured to minimize suggestive or evaluative wording and to present the questions in a neutral manner. Additionally, the anonymity of the responses helped lower perceived pressure, encouraging students to answer more spontaneously and authentically.

Another potential bias is **teacher influence bias**, meaning the possibility that the presence of the teacher could condition students' responses. To mitigate this risk, the Tutor teachers were limited to providing general instructions on completing the questionnaire without intervening in the content of the responses. Furthermore, the administration was carried out in a standardized setting, identical for all classes, thereby reducing variability in response conditions.

Finally, **non-response bias** was considered, referring to the risk that some students might omit answers or fail to complete the questionnaire. To address this issue, clear explanations were provided on the importance of the research and the value of each response, fostering greater engagement. Additionally, sufficient time was allocated for completion, allowing all students to respond calmly and thoughtfully.

The adoption of these strategies enabled the collection of higher-quality data, reducing the risk of distortions and ensuring greater reliability of the gathered information.

Questionnaire Structure

The questionnaire was designed as a standardized and structured instrument, aimed at systematically and consistently collecting information. Its construction was based on well-established models in educational and social research, following the methodological guidelines of Dillman et al. (2014) for the development of reliable surveys.

It consists of a series of closed-ended questions, divided into four main sections, each designed to investigate specific aspects of students' school experience and future perspectives. To ensure precise measurement and reduce the risk of bias in responses, various question formats were adopted, consistent with validated instruments in the literature, such as the **Approaches and Study Skills Inventory for Students (ASSIST; Entwistle & McCune, 2004)** and the **Career Adapt-Abilities Scale (CAAS; Savickas & Porfeli, 2012)**.

The questions were formulated clearly and accessibly, using three main types of items to ensure reliable and easily interpretable data collection:

- **Dichotomous questions (Yes/No)**

Used to collect categorical information about specific experiences, behaviors, or conditions.

Example: "Have you ever participated in a university or job orientation experience?"

Reference instrument: These questions are inspired by methodologies used in OECD-PISA self-assessment questionnaires (OECD, 2019), which measure students' engagement in educational and career orientation activities.

- **Multiple-choice questions with predefined answers**

Designed to collect data on preferences, opinions, and individual pathways.

Example: "Which of the following school activities do you find most useful for your professional development?" with options such as "Company internship," "Laboratory activities," "Orientation programs," "Extracurricular projects."

Reference instrument: Modeled after the **Career Adapt-Abilities Scale (CAAS; Savickas & Porfeli, 2012)**, used to analyze students' career adaptability.

- **5-point Likert scales**

Used to measure attitudes, perceptions, and levels of agreement/disagreement with specific statements.

Example: "To what extent do you feel prepared to enter the job market?" with responses on a scale from 1 (Not at all) to 5 (Very much).

Reference instrument: This type of question aligns with the **Student Engagement Instrument (Appleton et al., 2006)**, used to assess students' academic engagement.

The reliability of the questionnaire was tested through a **pilot phase**, conducted on a small sample of students with characteristics similar to those of the target population. This phase allowed for evaluating the clarity of the questions and the adequacy of the response formats. The internal reliability of the instrument was measured using **Cronbach's Alpha coefficient**, with values above 0.70 indicating good internal consistency (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994).

The adoption of these strategies allowed for refining the questionnaire before the final administration, ensuring that the questions were clear, relevant, and capable of collecting reliable and valid data.

Section	Objective	Question Type	Questions
1. Orientation and Future Choices	Investigate students' inclination towards further studies or entering the job market.	- Multiple choice	- "What do you plan to do after graduation?"
		- Likert Scale (1-5)	- "Which factors most influence your choice?"
			- "How confident do you feel about your choice?" (Likert 1-5)
2. Aspirations and Career Expectations	Analyze career ambitions and perception of future opportunities.	- Multiple choice	- "In which sector would you like to work?"
		- Likert Scale (1-5)	- "What difficulties do you think you might encounter?"
			- "How well do you feel prepared to enter the job market?" (Likert 1-5)
3. Skills and Project Planning	Assess students' self-evaluation of acquired skills and project experience.	- Multiple choice	- "Which skills do you think you have developed the most?"
		- Likert Scale (1-5)	- "How capable do you feel of developing a project independently?" (Likert 1-5)
4. Definition of 'Masterpiece'	Explore students' perception of significant projects and personal achievements.	- Multiple choice	- "Have you ever completed a project that you consider a 'masterpiece'?"
			- "In which field?"

Data Analysis

The results derive from a combined analysis of descriptive and inferential methods to ensure an in-depth understanding of students' perceptions of the "capolavoro" project, as suggested by Creswell & Plano Clark (2017). The techniques used include frequency analysis, which helps identify recurring patterns in responses, mean and standard deviation analysis, useful for measuring the level of agreement/disagreement and response dispersion, and the chi-square test (χ^2), employed to verify the existence of significant differences between student groups (Agresti, 2013).

Furthermore, to ensure the internal consistency of the questionnaire, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used, a statistical indicator of response consistency, with an optimal value (>0.7) widely recognized as a reliability criterion (Cronbach, 1951; Tavakol & Dennick, 2011).

Frequency analysis highlighted general trends in students' responses, while the chi-square test allowed verification of whether these patterns significantly differed among groups. For example, the distribution of responses related to the perceived usefulness of the "capolavoro" was initially analyzed through percentage frequencies to identify the proportions of students with different perceptions. Subsequently, the chi-square test determined whether these differences were statistically significant between technical and vocational institutes. This methodological combination ensured greater robustness in interpreting the results, confirming or refuting the hypotheses formulated based on the descriptive analysis.

The data analysis was also inspired by theoretical models in the field of school guidance. For instance, Super's career development theory (1980) and Savickas' school-to-work transition model (2013) emphasize the importance of concrete formative experiences in post-diploma decision-making. Additionally, Kolb's experiential learning studies (1984) suggest that practical activities, such as internships and apprenticeships, have a more significant impact than theoretical exercises, confirming the findings of this study.

Results of the Section "Orientation and Future Choices"

- **70%** of students from technical and vocational institutes state that they are still uncertain about their future, despite participating in the "capolavoro" project.
- Only **15%** of students believe that the "capolavoro" project had a positive impact on their post-diploma path choice.
- **60%** of students say they decided their future mainly thanks to internships or university orientation experiences, while only **10%** cite the "capolavoro" project as a determining factor.

Method used: Frequency Analysis (%)

This methodology allowed for understanding the distribution of responses and identifying key trends among students. Frequencies provide a clear picture of the general perception of the "capolavoro's" usefulness. According to Babbie (2020), descriptive data analysis is essential for identifying recurring patterns and facilitating group comparisons.

Results of the Section "Aspirations and Career Expectations"

- **75%** of students from vocational institutes consider the "capolavoro" a creative experience but not very useful for concretely understanding job opportunities.
- **50%** of students from technical institutes claim to have received more useful information through direct experiences with companies or internships.
- **65%** of students in the tourism and graphic communication sectors perceive the "capolavoro" more as an academic exercise than as a practical career guidance experience.

Method used: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis

Applied to Likert scale questions, this technique measured the average level of agreement/disagreement and the variability of responses. The statement "**The 'capolavoro' was useful for my future choice**" received an average score of **2.3 out of 5** with a standard deviation of **1.1**, indicating that the perception is generally negative and responses show little variability. This approach is supported by studies by Likert (1932) and Field (2018), demonstrating how standard deviation helps understand data dispersion.

Results of the Section "Skills and Project Planning"

- **80%** of students believe they have developed technical and practical skills through laboratory activities and internships.
- Only **30%** of students state that they feel completely autonomous in developing a complex project.
- **55%** of students from vocational institutes believe that the "capolavoro" only partially contributed to improving their project skills.

Method used: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis

The assessment of skills was measured through Likert scale questions. For example, the question "**I feel autonomous in carrying out a project**" scored an average of **3.0 out of 5**, with a standard deviation of **1.2**, indicating moderate variability among responses.

Results of the Section "Definition of Capolavoro"

- **40%** of students state that they have completed a project they consider a "capolavoro."
- **60%** of students consider the "capolavoro" a school assignment rather than a significant personal achievement.
- The most frequently mentioned sectors for completing a "capolavoro" are **graphic design, mechanics, and tourism**.

Method used: Frequency Analysis (%)

The responses were analyzed through percentage distribution to understand students' perception of their "capolavoro" projects. The analysis shows that most students do not perceive the "capolavoro" as a personally significant project but rather as a guided school activity.

Rethinking the Capolavoro: Towards a More Effective Model for Career Guidance and Professional Growth

It is clear that the Capolavoro project needs to be rethought to assume a more significant role in students' career guidance and professional growth. The data show that, although the Capolavoro is perceived as a creative and academic experience, its impact on future choices is limited. Most students from both technical and vocational sectors do not consider the Capolavoro a determining factor for their future, instead giving greater importance to internships, apprenticeships, and university guidance.

To make the Capolavoro a truly effective tool, it would be beneficial to integrate the project with practical experiences that are closer to the needs of the labor market, such as direct collaborations with companies, professional bodies, and universities. Additionally, greater attention to the personalization of the pathway could help students develop skills that are more consistent with their aspirations and their field of study.

Another crucial aspect concerns feedback: 40% of students report never having received structured evaluations of the skills developed through the Capolavoro, making it less useful for career guidance purposes. The Capolavoro should represent the tangible outcome in which students' acquired skills materialize, offering a concrete opportunity to assess their preparation. This would allow tutors to support students in making choices that do not align with their course of study, helping them reflect on their inclinations and future prospects. It is essential to emphasize that this is only one stage in the educational journey and not a final decision, but it can serve as a tool to identify possible needs for reorientation or further exploration in specific fields.

Finally, to improve the effectiveness of the Capolavoro, a review of the adopted teaching model could be useful, based on scientific evidence and international best practices. The analysis of validity and reliability has already confirmed the need for a reformulation based on more rigorous criteria and appropriate measurement tools. An interdisciplinary approach, which combines theory and practice in a more structured way, could strengthen the educational value of the Capolavoro and make it a truly useful experience for students' future.

However, it is important to highlight that the Capolavoro, as well as the role of tutors and career advisors, may have a limited impact if not placed within a broader context. Students' choices do not depend solely on school activities but are strongly influenced by their family context, socio-cultural environment, and the opportunities available in their territory. For a truly effective intervention, it would be necessary to involve families and the community more actively, creating a guidance ecosystem that supports students in a broader and more continuous manner.

Study Limitations and Future Research Directions

Despite the analysis providing a clear picture of students' perceptions regarding the Capolavoro project, the study has some limitations that should be considered. One of the main limitations concerns the sample: the research was based on data collected from a limited number of technical-vocational sector institutes, which may not represent the entire student population. Future studies could expand the sample, including a greater

number of schools distributed across different geographical areas, to assess any differences related to territorial context or the specificities of various fields of study.

Another limitation is related to the methodology used. Although the integration of descriptive and inferential analyses allowed for robust results, the research relied mainly on quantitative data. Future studies could adopt a more in-depth mixed-methods approach, including interviews or focus groups with students, teachers, and partner companies to explore in more detail the perceptions and needs of the stakeholders involved.

Finally, it would be useful to investigate the long-term impact of the Capolavoro, monitoring students after graduation to understand whether and how this experience influenced their career and academic choices. A longitudinal follow-up could provide more solid data on the effectiveness of the Capolavoro as a career guidance tool, helping to identify improvement strategies based on empirical evidence.

Conclusions and Practical Implications

From a practical perspective, these results offer concrete insights for improving the effectiveness of the Capolavoro within the educational context. A first step could be to create stronger partnerships between schools, companies, and universities, allowing students to work on projects with a real impact on their professional path. For example, the Capolavoro could be designed as a business problem-solving project or a project that addresses a concrete challenge in the reference sector, thus strengthening the connection between theory and practice.

The adoption of an evaluation system that includes periodic feedback on the transversal skills acquired would help students develop a greater awareness of their abilities, improving their self-guidance process.

Another fundamental aspect concerns the involvement of families and the local community in the career guidance process. Creating a broader support ecosystem, in which schools, families, and the job market actively collaborate, could help reduce the gap between school training and labor market demands. For instance, organizing meetings with professionals, thematic workshops, or mentorship programs with industry experts could provide students with a clearer vision of the opportunities and possible career paths.

Finally, to ensure the continuous improvement of the Capolavoro, future studies could evaluate the impact of newly adopted strategies, analyzing whether and how they influence students' university and career choices.

In conclusion, the Capolavoro has the potential to become a significant tool for career guidance and professional growth, but achieving this goal requires a rethinking of the current model. Only through greater integration with the labor market, a more effective evaluation system, and active involvement of the educational

community will it be possible to transform the Capolavoro into a truly formative and useful experience for students' future.

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